

Hyperbaric Oxygen Therapy (HBOT) as a Potential Strategy for the Prevention and Treatment of Alzheimer's disease: A Review of Recent Research

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Abstract— Alzheimer's disease (AD) is the leading cause of dementia, and with the global aging of the population, the number of cases is increasing. Pharmacological therapy is the primary strategy for treating AD, but available medications only alleviate the symptoms of the disease, highlighting the need to explore alternative methods. Recent studies indicate that therapies affecting oxygen metabolism are a promising strategy for treating AD. This study aims to review the latest research on hyperbaric oxygen therapy (HBOT) as a potential method for preventing and treating AD. A literature search was conducted using the medical databases PubMed and Google Scholar. Articles were retrieved in English, employing the keywords: „Alzheimer's disease”, „hypoxia”, „hyperbaric oxygen therapy”, „neuroprotection”, „cognition”. Hypoxia has been identified as a risk factor for AD, exacerbating the pathological processes underlying the disease. Recent studies suggest that HBOT alleviates brain hypoxia, offering multifaceted beneficial effects on the complex pathology of AD and counteracting the molecular mechanisms of neurodegeneration. Additionally, its benefits in treating conditions that contribute to the development of AD have been demonstrated, highlighting its neuroprotective potential. Numerous studies suggest the benefits of using HBOT in patients with AD, and the implementation of this therapy in clinical practice may offer a new strategy for the prevention and treatment of AD.

Keywords— Alzheimer's disease; hypoxia; hyperbaric oxygen therapy; neuroprotection; cognition;

1. INTRODUCTION AND PURPOSE

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is widely recognized as the leading cause of dementia and the most common neurodegenerative disorder [1]. With the global aging of the population, the number of cases continues to rise, increasing the burden on individual, social, and economic levels [2]. According to projections by the World Health Organization (WHO), by 2040, neurodegenerative diseases will become the second most common cause of death in developed countries, following cardiovascular diseases [3]. Pharmacological therapy is currently the primary strategy for treating Alzheimer's dementia. However, available drugs show limited efficacy in alleviating symptoms and have little impact on slowing disease progression. Consequently, non-pharmacological therapy is gaining increasing attention as a potentially effective alternative for the treatment of AD. Numerous studies indicate that hypoxia plays a key role as an environmental factor promoting the development of AD. Recent reports suggest that hyperbaric oxygen therapy (HBOT), which focuses on reducing hypoxia, may offer a promising therapeutic option

for AD patients in the future [4,5]. This study aims to review the latest research on hyperbaric oxygen therapy (HBOT) as a potential method for preventing and treating AD.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A comprehensive review of the literature was performed by searching through databases such as PubMed and Google Scholar. Articles were retrieved employing the keywords: „Alzheimer's disease”, „hypoxia”, „hyperbaric oxygen therapy”, „neuroprotection”, „cognition”. The search included articles published from 2015 to 2025. Frequently cited publications published earlier were also included. Only publications in the English language were considered for inclusion.

3. STATE OF KNOWLEDGE

A. Alzheimer's Disease

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is the most common neurodegenerative disease, accounting for 60-80% of all cases of such disorders. At the beginning of the 21st century, more than 35 million people suffered from AD, and it is currently estimated that the disease affects 50 million people worldwide. Projections indicate that this number will triple, reaching 152 million by 2050 [6,7]. Additionally, AD is the most common cause of dementia, responsible for about 60-90% of all dementia cases. Among individuals aged 65-70, the risk of developing dementia is 1 in 100 annually, and after the age of 80, it increases to 4 in 100 annually, with the prevalence in men being 19-29% lower than in women [8,9]. As a result of this disease, there is a gradual decline in cognitive functions and the occurrence of psychobehavioral disorders. The central neuropathology of this condition is considered to be the progressive degeneration of neurons and synapses in the brain, caused by the accumulation of beta-amyloid ($A\beta$) deposits and phosphorylated tau protein neurofibrillary tangles [6,10]. Amyloid plaques in individuals with AD are formed through the processing of amyloid precursor protein (APP) by β - and γ -secretase enzymes. Tau protein stabilizes microtubules, and its hyperphosphorylation, caused by disruptions in the activity of kinases and phosphatases, prevents its proper interaction with microtubules, leading to axonal dysfunction [11,12,13]. Although AD was discovered over 100 years ago, its complex molecular mechanisms are still not fully understood. It is currently believed that key pathophysiological factors include vascular abnormalities, oxidative stress, mitochondrial dysfunction, impaired autophagy, glucose hypometabolism in the brain, and neuroinflammation [7,11]. In individuals with AD, autophagy dysfunction has been observed, which is responsible for the degradation of abnormal proteins and serves a cytoprotective function against oxidative stress [14]. Mitochondrial dysfunction plays a critical role in the pathogenesis of AD and is due to decreased membrane potential, increased permeability, and excessive production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which cause mutations in mitochondrial DNA and lead to defects in mitochondrial biogenesis [15]. Microglia and astrocytes interact with $A\beta$, leading to their uncontrolled activation and the release of inflammatory mediators, increasing the risk of neurotoxicity and neuroinflammation. Additionally, it has been shown that regional reduction in cerebral blood flow (CBF) and local glucose hypometabolism are among the earliest functional changes preceding cognitive decline in AD [16,17]. Despite the increasing number of AD cases, there has been no significant progress in the treatment of this disease. The available medications only alleviate symptoms and include modulators of cholinergic neurotransmission, which are used at every stage of the disease, such as acetylcholinesterase inhibitors (donepezil, rivastigmine, and galantamine). Additionally, there are modulators of glutamatergic neurotransmission, including memantine, which is a partial antagonist of the N-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA) receptor, used in moderate to severe stages [6,9,18,19]. New drugs being developed for AD therapy have various mechanisms of action, including inhibiting the enzymes that process APP into $A\beta$, reducing the influx of $A\beta$ into neurons, and decreasing insulin resistance. However, these drugs have not yet been introduced into medical practice due to failures in clinical trials. Monoclonal antibodies, such as aducanumab, donanemab, lecanemab, and gantenerumab, are also being investigated with the aim of

reducing A β aggregation. Some of these antibodies may be associated with significant side effects, such as hemosiderosis or amyloid-related imaging abnormalities (ARIA) resulting from edema (ARIA-E) or hemorrhage (ARIA-H). Clinical trials are also underway for tau aggregation inhibitors, such as methylthionine and leucomethylthionine [9,20,21,22]. There is growing interest in identifying alternative therapeutic targets that affect AD pathology, driven by the lack of effective disease-modifying treatments and highlighting the need to explore new forms of therapy. According to recent studies, hyperbaric oxygen therapy (HBOT) may be a promising therapeutic strategy for AD, alleviating the underlying disease mechanisms [5,6].

B. Oxygen Metabolism Disorders in Alzheimer's Disease

Increasing evidence suggests that disruptions in oxygen metabolism are significant factors contributing to the pathophysiological changes leading to the development of AD [23,24]. Studies have shown that hypoxia can exacerbate A β accumulation and promote the aggregation of hyperphosphorylated tau protein by increasing the activity of secretases, decreasing the expression of neprilysin (NEP), and insulin-degrading enzymes (IDE), which are crucial for A β degradation. Additionally, hypoxia reduces the expression of low-density lipoprotein receptor-related protein 1 (LRP-1), which is responsible for the clearance of A β across the blood-brain barrier (BBB) [25,26,27,28,29]. It has been documented that hypoxia increases hippocampal neuron apoptosis in rodents, which is associated with tau hyperphosphorylation via the Orai1/CDK5 pathway. In a mouse model of AD, acute hypoxia increased the expression of APP, APH1 (anterior pharynx-defective 1), and CDK5 (Cyclin-dependent kinase 5), promoting tau phosphorylation. An increase in the components of the electron transport chain in mitochondria was also observed, indicating dysfunction following acute hypoxia. Additionally, there was increased activity of pro-inflammatory cytokines and M1 microglia markers, as well as decreased activity of anti-inflammatory cytokines and M2 microglia markers, in the hippocampus and cerebral cortex of hypoxic mice, indicating that hypoxia activates microglia and exacerbates neuroinflammation [30,31,32]. It has also been shown that both acute and chronic oxygen deficiency disrupt autophagy by modulating mTOR signaling pathways. Furthermore, hypoxia can damage the BBB, which exacerbates AD neuropathology [11,31,33]. Brain hypoxia can be caused by environmental and pathological factors such as aging, cerebrovascular diseases, hypertension, type 2 diabetes, traumatic brain injury (TBI), and respiratory diseases, which are major risk factors for AD. Both acute hypoxia resulting from ischemic stroke or traumatic brain injury (TBI) and prolonged oxygen deficiency caused by chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) or obstructive sleep apnea syndrome (OSAS) can be harmful to the brain [23,34,35].

C. Hyperbaric Oxygen Therapy (HBOT)

Hyperbaric oxygen therapy (HBOT) was first described in 1662, and its popularity significantly increased as a method for treating decompression sickness. It is a non-invasive therapy that involves breathing 100% oxygen at atmospheric pressure exceeding 1 ATA [36]. During HBOT, a pressure of 2.0–2.5 ATA is applied, and the number and duration of sessions vary depending on the condition being treated. Inhaling 100% oxygen at a pressure of 3 ATA increases the partial pressure of oxygen to 2000 mmHg, and the amount of oxygen delivered to tissues increases from 3 to 60 ml per liter of blood. This results in an excess of oxygen in the bloodstream, allowing for its efficient transport to tissues without the involvement of erythrocytes [5,37]. This mechanism leads to a range of health benefits, making HBOT useful in treating non-healing wounds such as diabetic foot ulcers, burns, radiation injuries, decompression sickness, air embolism, carbon monoxide poisoning, vascular disorders, and as a rehabilitation method [38]. Recent studies suggest that HBOT may have neuroprotective effects in neurodegenerative diseases, including AD. By increasing oxygen delivery to the brain, this form of treatment can support mitochondrial function, reduce oxidative stress, and alleviate neuroinflammation, which synergistically contributes to maintaining neuronal integrity and

improving cognitive functions [5]. An important role in the effects of HBOT is attributed to the "hyperoxic–hypoxic paradox", which involves increasing oxygen concentration to 100% with a subsequent drop to 21% at the end of each session. The increased oxygen availability in tissues activates Nrf2 (nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2), which mediates the repair and degradation of damaged proteins, activates antioxidant pathways, modulates the inflammatory response, and activates the Bcl-2 family of proteins, enhancing synaptic plasticity and inhibiting neuronal apoptosis [39,40,41]. The subsequent return to normal oxygen concentration (21%) is perceived by cells as hypoxia, which activates HIF1 α (hypoxia-inducible factor 1), involved in angiogenesis, vascular remodeling, and inhibition of apoptosis [42]. Both factors, Nrf2 and HIF1 α , interact with a common target protein, heme oxygenase-1 (HO-1), known as a heat shock protein (HSP32), which protects against oxidative damage and regulates cell proliferation [43]. Mitochondria are the primary biological target of HBOT, and an important mechanism promoted during therapy is the transport of mitochondria from astrocytes to neurons, which reduces secondary neuronal cell death induced by inflammation [44]. Additionally, HBOT may increase the secretion of humanin, a newly discovered mitochondrial protein with neuroprotective properties. Although the mechanism of this action is unclear, it may involve the activation of autophagy, improvement of mitochondrial function, and reduction of insulin resistance [45,46,47]. HBOT increases neuronal proliferation in the hippocampus and subventricular zone, supports their regeneration after brain injuries, and stimulates angiogenesis, likely through enhanced VEGF/ERK signaling [38,48,49]. Additionally, HBOT promotes the mobilization of bone marrow stem cells to ischemic areas of the brain and the release of trophic factors that support neurogenesis [50]. These processes can increase CBF and support cognitive functions, as confirmed in both animal and human studies [51].

HBOT promotes the reduction of neuroinflammation by increasing the levels of anti-inflammatory interleukins IL-10 and IL-4 and decreasing the secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF α (tumor necrosis factor α), which correlates with improvements in cognitive deficits [38,52,53,54]. HBOT also exhibits significant neuroprotective potential by increasing the expression of SIRT1 (NAD-dependent deacetylase sirtuin-1), Nrf2, HO-1, and SOD1 (superoxide dismutase), while reducing levels of MDA (malondialdehyde), suggesting its role in enhancing antioxidant defense pathways [55]. Considering these neuroprotective mechanisms, HBOT may lead to clinical improvement in patients with AD.

D. Impact of HBOT on the Pathophysiological Mechanisms of Alzheimer's Disease

Numerous studies have demonstrated that HBOT can alleviate many of the mechanisms underlying AD, increasing its significance as a potential strategy and new approach in the therapy of patients with AD [5].

D.1 Impact of HBOT on Amyloid- β Metabolism and Tau Protein Hyperphosphorylation

Results from multiple studies indicate that HBOT can effectively inhibit the deposition of A β plaques and the aggregation of hyperphosphorylated tau protein, leading to reduced degeneration of neurons and synapses in the studied rodents [51,53,56,57,58,59,60]. Shapira et al. demonstrated that HBOT significantly reduced amyloid burden in the hippocampus of 5XFAD mice, as evidenced by a decrease in the number ($p=0.0217$) and size ($p=0.0125$) of amyloid plaques and a reduction in the levels of insoluble A β 42 and A β 40. Furthermore, it reduced A β synthesis by lowering the levels of BACE1 and presenilin-1 and increased the activity of A β degradation and clearance pathways, resulting in elevated levels of IDE and LRP1 [51]. In an earlier study on 3xTg mice, Shapira et al. also noted a reduction in amyloid burden and tau phosphorylation following HBOT [53]. Similarly, Chen et al. observed a significant reduction in the expression of genes associated with A β , such as APP, BACE1, and cathepsin β mRNA, along with an increase in the expression of NEP and IDE, under the influence of HBOT in an aging mouse model [59].

D.2 Impact of HBOT on Oxidative Stress

Studies have also shown that HBOT strongly mobilizes the antioxidant enzyme system and supports protection against damage caused by reactive oxygen species (ROS), which is attributed to the increased activity of antioxidant enzymes such as PRDX3 (thioredoxin-dependent peroxide reductase), SOD, and GSH (glutathione) [57,61,62,63,64]. In an aging mouse model subjected to HBOT, an improvement in behavioral outcomes was noted, partially attributed to the reduction of oxidative stress [59]. It is worth noting that HBOT may initially induce moderate oxidative stress, which activates the body's defense mechanisms, increasing tissue resistance to future damage [65].

D.3 Impact of HBOT on Neuronal Apoptosis

Scientific data indicate that HBOT has protective potential against neuronal loss [10,59,60,66,67,68]. In a study by Zhao et al., a five-day HBOT treatment in a rat model of AD reduced neuronal damage and apoptosis in the CA1 region of the hippocampus and prevented the loss of dendritic spines, likely by inhibiting the p38 mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) pathway, whose activation worsens the course of AD [66]. In two other studies, HBOT was found to reduce neuronal cell damage and decrease the hippocampal neuron apoptosis index in AD rats by limiting the activation of the NF- κ B pathway and inhibiting mitochondria-dependent apoptosis [10,68]. HBOT also alleviated cognitive impairment in an aging mouse model by increasing the expression of Bcl-2 and decreasing the levels of pro-apoptotic peptides Bax and caspase-3 [59]. Furthermore, HBOT has been shown to enhance autophagy through the activation of the AMPK-mTOR pathway [60].

D.4 Impact of HBOT on Mitochondrial Function

It is suggested that HBOT exerts its beneficial effects through protective action on mitochondria [44,47,63,68,69,70]. In a study by Xu et al., patients with vascular dementia who underwent 12 weeks of HBOT showed a significant increase in serum humanin levels ($p < 0.05$), which positively correlated with MMSE test scores (Spearman correlation $r = 0.409$, $p < 0.05$) [47]. The neuroprotective mechanism of HBOT is believed to involve preserving mitochondrial integrity and reducing the mitochondrial apoptotic pathway, as confirmed in studies on rodents with cortical injuries treated with oxygen therapy [69]. It has also been shown that short-term HBOT (1-5 sessions) can decrease the integrity of the electron transport chain and initiate the mitochondrial apoptotic pathway, but these effects do not occur with long-term treatment [63].

D.5 Impact of HBOT on Neuroinflammation

Numerous reports suggest that HBOT may beneficially affect the reduction of inflammation in the nervous system [52,53,56,66]. Shapira et al. observed that a 2-week HBOT regimen in 3xTg mice alleviated neuroinflammation by reducing astrogliosis, microgliosis, and pro-inflammatory cytokine production, while promoting the secretion of anti-inflammatory cytokines [53]. Similar results were obtained with a 3-month HBOT treatment, which reduced the activation of microglia, astrocytes, and the levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines in the hippocampus of mice with early-stage AD [56].

D.6 Impact of HBOT on Neurotrophic Factors

Research highlights that neurotrophic factors such as BDNF (brain-derived neurotrophic factor) and neurotrophins (NT3, NT4/5) play an important role in maintaining synaptic plasticity. Higher serum levels of BDNF are also correlated with improved cognitive function in AD [57,71]. Choi et al. observed that HBOT reversed the decrease in the expression of BDNF, NT3, NT4/5, and the receptor TrkB (tropomyosin receptor kinase B) in Tg-APP/PS1 mice. They also noted an increase in the expression of myelination markers (Mbp, myelin-associated oligodendrocytic basic protein, and Mog, myelin oligodendrocyte

glycoprotein), the dendritic marker MAP2 (microtubule-associated protein 2), and neurogenesis markers (DCX, doublecortin, and Ki-67, antigen Kiel 67) [57]. Another study found increased expression of PSD95 (postsynaptic density protein 95), BDNF, and Syn (synaptophysin) proteins in aging C57BL/6 mice after 14 days of HBOT, indicating improved neural network function [60].

D.7 Impact of HBOT on Cerebral Blood Flow

Studies show that hyperoxygenation under increased atmospheric pressure benefits brain health by improving the function of the BBB and stimulating angiogenesis [36,51,56,57,72]. In a mouse model of early AD, long-term HBOT resulted in a significant increase in CBF and improvement in the structure and function of cerebral vessels, alleviating brain ischemia and microvascular damage [56]. In 5XFAD mice subjected to HBOT, a significant increase in the lumen diameter of blood vessels in the hippocampus ($p=0.016$) and cerebral cortex ($p=0.0064$) was observed, along with a significant decrease in HIF1 α levels ($p=0.0056$), indicating improved blood perfusion and reduced hypoxia. These changes persisted for 2 weeks after the last session, suggesting a long-term effect [51]. In Tg-APP/PS1 mice, 1-hour hyperoxygenation for 28 days reduced the expression of hypoxia-related markers such as HIF1 α , Hmox1 (heme oxygenase 1 gene), and Pdk2 (pyruvate dehydrogenase kinase isoform 2). An increased cerebral blood volume under hyperoxic conditions was also observed in the J20-hAPP mouse model of AD ($p=0.0002$) [57,72].

E. Impact of HBOT on Cognitive Function in Humans

Recent studies in humans have shown that HBOT can improve cognitive functions in patients with mild cognitive impairment (MCI) and AD. Chen et al. evaluated the impact of HBOT on 42 patients with AD and 11 with MCI through twenty 40-minute sessions administered once daily. Cognitive functions were assessed after 1, 3, and 6 months using the Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE), Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA), and Activities of Daily Living (ADL) tests. In patients with MCI, one cycle of HBOT significantly improved MoCA scores after one and three months ($p < 0.05$ and $p = 0.059$, respectively) and MMSE scores after three months ($p < 0.05$). For patients with AD, the HBOT cycle resulted in significant improvements in cognitive function, as assessed by MMSE and MoCA, after one month ($p < 0.05$). Additionally, ADL scores were significantly higher in these patients after one and three months. Moreover, it was documented that HBOT also alleviated glucose hypometabolism in some patients with AD and MCI. However, no long-term improvement in cognitive function was observed in AD patients after more than one month, suggesting that HBOT temporarily alleviates cognitive dysfunction [4]. Harch et al. described a case of a 58-year-old woman with rapidly progressing AD who was treated with HBOT. After 9 weeks of therapy, including 40 sessions, a significant increase in global brain metabolism (by 6.5-38%) was observed in areas with metabolic deficits detected by fluorodeoxyglucose PET (FDG-PET). The patient showed significant improvement in symptoms such as energy, mood, memory, concentration, sleep quality, and a reduction in anxiety and disorientation. After 2 months, there was a mild recurrence of symptoms, which was stabilized with intermittent HBOT sessions, normobaric oxygen, and pharmacotherapy [73]. Shapira et al. conducted a study in which 6 elderly patients with significant memory impairments underwent 3 months of HBOT (a total of 60 daily sessions). The participants showed a significant increase in CBF in several brain regions and a significant improvement in global cognitive scores ($p=0.004$). The greatest improvements were noted in memory, attention, and information processing speed [51]. Several studies evaluating the impact of HBOT on cognitive function have also been conducted among healthy individuals. Yu et al. conducted a study among 20 healthy students. The experimental group was administered hyperbaric oxygen (HBO), after which significantly better cognitive function scores, including memory, were observed compared to the control group [74]. Similarly, Hadanny et al. demonstrated that a 3-month HBOT regimen improves cognitive performance in healthy older adults, which was linked to regional increases in CBF. The most significant changes were observed in attention, information processing speed, and executive functions [75].

F. Impact of HBOT on Cognitive Function in Animals

There are studies in the literature indicating neurobehavioral improvement in rodents subjected to HBOT, suggesting potential benefits of this method in modulating brain function and supporting neuronal regeneration [5,51,53,56,57,58,60,66]. Yang et al. observed that a 3-month HBOT intervention in a mouse model of early-stage AD (APP^{swe}/PS1^{dE9} AD) alleviated cognitive dysfunction [56]. In a study on 5xFAD mice, Mensah-Kane et al. found that HBOT improved cognitive performance and associative learning only in female rodents. Furthermore, the therapy reversed AD-related balance impairments but had no effect on gait, running, or anxiety disorders [5]. Shapira et al. observed that 1-hour HBOT sessions for 2 weeks alleviated behavioral deficits in 3xTg mice [53]. HBOT also improved memory and reduced behavioral disturbances in 5XFAD mice [51]. Wang et al. reported improvements in spatial memory and learning abilities in aging C57BL/6 mice after 2 weeks of HBOT [60].

G. Impact of HBOT on Alzheimer's Disease Risk Factors

Many disease processes, such as aging, respiratory diseases, stroke, and TBI, synergistically promote hypoxia, which contributes to the development of AD [23]. Increasing evidence suggests that oxygen therapy can improve the clinical condition of patients with various disorders and counteract AD risk factors.

G.1 Impact of HBOT on Aging Processes

Aging is the most significant risk factor in the pathophysiology of AD and involves cellular mechanisms such as telomere shortening, oxidative stress, DNA damage, and chromatin disturbances [76]. Studies also point to less typical mechanisms that accelerate brain aging, such as disrupted insulin signaling caused by insulin resistance [77]. In a study by Hachmo et al., it was observed that repeated HBOT sessions in healthy older adults led to a significant extension of telomeres in T, NK, and B cells and a reduction in the percentage of senescent helper T cells [78,79]. Wang et al. observed a marked increase in the number of synapses, improved synaptic integrity, and reduced demyelination in a group of aging mice subjected to 2 weeks of HBOT, suggesting its beneficial effects on synaptic plasticity, remyelination, and reduction of age-related synapse loss, contributing to improved cognitive function in aging mice. Additionally, in the hippocampus of rodents treated with HBOT, a reduction in the number of cells with increased expression of β -galactosidase, a marker of cellular aging, was noted [60]. In one study, HBOT restored insulin sensitivity and alleviated cognitive impairment and aging processes in the hippocampus of rats with insulin resistance, as well as in a rat model of aging [80]. These data suggest that HBOT may alleviate the symptoms of aging and delay the development of AD.

G.2 Impact of HBOT on the Effects of Ischemic Stroke and Traumatic Brain Injury

Ischemic stroke and TBI are risk factors for the development of AD, and studies suggest that HBOT can regenerate damaged brain tissue [5,81]. In a small group of post-stroke patients who underwent 20 HBOT sessions over 4 weeks, significant improvements in memory, executive functions, and gait were observed, and participants also reported a better quality of life [82]. Two other studies on larger groups of post-stroke patients who underwent 40 HBOT sessions showed significant neurological and cognitive improvement, even in the chronic phase of the disease [83,84]. Boussi-Gross et al., in a retrospective analysis of data from 91 patients who experienced a stroke 3-180 months prior to HBOT, demonstrated significant improvement ($p < 0.0005$) in all memory parameters, correlated with improved brain metabolism [85]. In another study, although patients with stroke, anoxia, and brain injury reported improvements in cognitive functions after 60 HBOT sessions, no clinically significant changes were observed in standardized tests. However, improved brain perfusion was observed in CT angiography [86]. The results suggest that HBOT may reduce the effects of stroke by developing ischemic tolerance and preventing neuronal death [65]. The use of HBOT in cases of TBI also positively affects damaged or inactive neurons by increasing CBF and improving

oxygenation, which supports their metabolic reactivation [87]. Tal et al. observed that HBOT increases CBF, promotes cerebral angiogenesis, neuroplasticity, and nerve fiber regeneration, leading to improved cognitive outcomes in patients with TBI [88,89]. Other studies have provided similar results, indicating the restoration of impaired brain functions and overall cognitive improvement in patients with TBI undergoing HBOT [90,91,92].

G.3 Oxygen Therapy in Respiratory Diseases

Studies suggest that obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) may lead to neurodegenerative changes through intermittent hypoxia and sleep fragmentation, promoting the development of AD [93]. In patients with COPD, resting hypoxemia is observed as a significant risk factor for cognitive impairment [94,95]. Continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP), as the optimal therapy for OSA, restores tissue oxygenation and may delay the onset of cognitive impairment and neurodegenerative changes in patients with AD, just as regular oxygen therapy alleviates hypoxemia and reduces the risk of cognitive impairment ($p < 0.0001$) in patients with COPD [95,96]. These data suggest that oxygen therapy could be a strategy for preventing or delaying the development of AD.

H. Adverse Effects of HBOT

HBOT is considered a safe and routinely used medical procedure, and its side effects are usually self-limiting and can be avoided with proper patient selection. The most common adverse effects include middle ear barotrauma, headaches, and claustrophobic anxiety. Most complications associated with HBOT are mild and reversible after treatment, and severe complications, such as oxygen toxicity leading to temporary loss of consciousness or seizures, are extremely rare and occur at pressures above 2.4 ATA [4,37]. Pulmonary oxygen toxicity, which can lead to edema and hemorrhage followed by fibrosis and reduced vital capacity, may be observed in intensive treatment regimens for decompression sickness but not in daily HBOT for other indications. The risk of hyperoxic myopia exists with regular HBOT, but this condition is reversible. Special caution should be taken in patients with heart failure and aortic stenosis due to the potential for hypotension [97].

4. CONCLUSIONS

Hyperbaric oxygen therapy (HBOT) shows potential as a new approach in the therapy of Alzheimer's disease (AD) by alleviating various pathological mechanisms underlying the condition. Numerous studies confirm the benefits of HBOT in patients with dementia, and the implementation of this therapy in clinical practice may contribute to modifying the course of the disease, making it a promising option for the treatment and prevention of AD. These findings highlight the need for further research to fully understand and utilize the neuroprotective potential of HBOT.

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